

"TOMARIS AND SHIROK UZBEK NATIONAL HEROES"

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ANNOTATION:

In this article, in the image of "Tomaris and Shirak Uzbek folk heroes", we will discuss the history of our people through another artist Mirkarim Osim, such as writing folklore and their courage.

KEYWORDS:

Tomaris, Shirak, Sak and Massaget, Cyrus II, Dorothy, People, Heroes, Greek, Founder.

Folk epics are the priceless spiritual wealth of the nation. People have created legends about many heroes they love and admire. Their strength, courage, first, the notorious oral form of the coming of the Lords, later Epic written forms of motivation. In the heroic epics, which were born as examples of folk art, unique images of patriotic, brave national heroes were created. Heroes such as Tomaris, Shirak, Zarina, Rustam are such images that have won the love of the Uzbek people. Such heroes, loved by the people, have a special place in the literature of each nation. Their names live on in people's hearts for centuries. Methods. Common features of ancient Uzbek and English epics. This article tells about the secrets of the life of immortal characters such as the heroes of ancient and famous legends of the Uzbek people Tomaris, Shirak, Sparganiz, Rustam and the hero of the English epic Beowulf. The article mentioned in the book, and they described the unique features of heroes, a separate distinct aspect of the

nation and other nations to generalize the heroes of consciousness, comparative and analytical methods.

Tomaris (6th century BC) was a brave female commander who led the Turanian people in their struggle against the Achaemenid invasion. Qad. According to the Greek historian Herodotus's "History" (5th century BC), the founder of the Achaemenid state, Cyrus II. av. When she invaded Turan in 530, Tomaris was the queen of the Massaget tribe. The Massagets lived at this time on the banks of the Amudarya (Araks) and in the Kyzylkum. Tomaris was the wife of the king of the Massagets, who ruled the country after her husband's death. Undaunted by his son's death, Tomaris, in the interests of his people, asked Cyrus II to leave the land of the Massagets. However, when the Persian king refused, a fierce battle ensued. Herodotus describes the battle between the Massagetes and the Persians in the following way: "As far as I know, this battle was the worst of all the battles between the barbarians. The battle lasted a long time. There was a lot of bloodshed. Finally, the Massagets won. Most of the Persian army, including Cyrus II, died on the battlefield. She reigned for 29 years. (Tomaris) ordered his severed head to be placed in a mesh filled with human blood. " Folk epics, battles and legends were written about Tomaris's courage and military-political activity. In the epic "Oysuluv" written by Ergash Jumanbulbul's son Hodi Zarifov, Tomaris's work finds its artistic interpretation in the image of Oysuluv, the king of the Turan country. Writer Mirkarim Osim praises his courage in the story "Tomaris". Ibrahim Yusupov wrote the epic "Tomaris" (1974), composer Ulugbek Musayev staged the ballet of the same name (1982). It is clear that the courage of women is important and necessary to bring up generations like Tomaris in Uzbekistan, where we live today.

In the image of "Tomaris and Shirak Uzbek national heroes" to write the theme of history, which we convey to our people through another artist, requires great knowledge, observation and skill. As Mirkarim Osim begins to work in this direction, he will study the history of our ancestors in detail. Like divers searching for pearls in the sea, they dive into the ocean of the past and pick up words. Thus, his works "Tomaris", "Shirak", "Dedicated to the Book", "Temur Malik", "Light in the Darkness" were born.

The first of them is "Tomaris". As soon as the work begins, Mirkarim Asim's mastery of words and vivid portrayal of nature captivate: "The bride of the desert spring is a foot. He spread a green floor decorated with flowers under it." At the beginning of the work, it is mentioned that in the traditions of that time, the "bride" ceremony was held and held. Before the wedding, the bride and groom fight. The image of the struggle between men and women is astonishing on the one hand, and on the other hand, we can feel that women are as strong as men.

The story follows the events following the arrival of the ambassadors and introduces the people of Massaget and their relationship to their way of life. In other words, the simple dress of Tomaris, who seemed unusual to the ambassadors of Caiaphas, and the fact that he ate with the people show the humility of the Massaget people and the arrogance of their rulers. Tomaris's masculine courage and patriotism can be seen in his fearless response to the ambassador: "I do not want to be a slave to him, to enslave my people to him."

In this story, one can see how powerful Caiaphas was, how big his neighbors were, and how well his commanders knew the tricks of war. At first, the masseurs overcome the last part of it, but those who do not taste the wine, lose their victories. Caiaphas recaptures them while intoxicated. Caiaphas tries to release Siparangiz, the son of Tomaris, the leader of the Massaget troops, in spite of his insults, but he prefers death to honoring his defeat as a betrayal of his people, and stabs himself to death.

The great loss that has aroused the hatred of the people, the terrible massacre that has shaken the people. Tomaris leads them, prays to God for salvation, and defeats them. Caiaphas' head is dipped in blood. In this play we can see the following qualities of the people of Massaget:

- Solidarity (Tomaris sees the people as his family);
- Courage (same courage in men and women)
- Courage (women and men go to war without fear);
- Caring (sharing everything with the people;)
- Humility;
- Not arrogant;

There are so many types it's hard to say. We can say that the work is a monument to the life of the Massaget people, to the courage of Tomaris.

Shirak also recreates the story of a brave son of the Shak (Sak) people. At the beginning of the work we find information about the lifestyle of the nomads, the existence of epics among them. In the play, we can see Shirak's bravery several times. He cuts off his ears and noses and endures all his sufferings for his people. He gives his life for his country. He is not only a patriot, but also an experienced man who has seen a lot. Shirak, for example, entered a meeting with the tribal elders and Rustak and asked the elders to leave so as not to spread rumors.

Shirak convinces Droni of his plan and leads his troops into the desert. When Dorothy's army learned of his plan, they surrounded him and beat him. After a while, the commander tries to give him another chance, but as the man says, he will not break his oath to his people.

He is a brave son of the Shirak people and sacrificed his life for the liberation of the people. He is a role model for every child in every country. The above-mentioned stories of Mirkarim Osim skillfully depict the spirituality, behavior, and customs of the Sak and Massaget peoples, which indicates that the writer has studied history well.

In short, there is no future without history, that is, every day that passes is history for us. It is necessary to draw conclusions from this past day and draw good educational conclusions from how brave, knowledgeable, courageous and disciplined our ancestors were.

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